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Resumen y palabras clave:

The essay approaches the scientific model as was presented by Georg Friedrich Puchta in the context of the methodological renewal that characterized the early nineteenth century Germany. In this spirit of Modernisierung, the figure of Savignys emblematic disciple stood out. Puchta developed a Law of Science ('Recht der Wissenschaft') that had a great reception among most important jurists of the century (Thöl, Gerber, Jhering, Goldschmidt). Legal analogy was of particular importance among the instruments that served this scientification. However, the legal science of the time combined a high technical character with an almost absolute absence of methodological rules. The rejection (very clear in Puchta's doctrine) of the nascent methodology (Thibaut) can be better understood from the core idea that defines this legal philosophy: that history is the essence of law, and hence that only a rich historical legal knowledge, and not aprioristic methodological rules, can serve as methodus.

Keywords: Pandectist studies, legal analogy, legal hermeneutics, Georg Friedrich Puchta. Pandectística, analogía jurídica, hermenéutica jurídica, Georg Friedrich Puchta.